

					KEEPING	Removing																
					1	Primary							Secondary					17				
Algorithm	Code	Parameters	Caliper	Code Replace?	All Pri + Sec All Primary	Location	Tribes	Age	Main Income	Education	Elephant Losses	Distance to NP	Support from NGOs	Wealth	Rainfall	Gender	Household	Frequency of Elephants	Sleep with elephants	Farmer mitigation effort		
1	Genetic Matching	0.1 1 Nearest Neighbour	None	Yes	Gen	1.1	2.1	3.1	4.1	5.1	6.1	7.1	8.1	9.1	10.1	11.1	12.1	13.1	14.1	15.1	16.1	17.1
2	Genetic Matching	0.2	0.25 SD Caliper	Yes	Gen	1.2	2.2	3.2	4.2	5.2	6.2	7.2	8.2	9.2	10.2	11.2	12.2	13.2	14.2	15.2	16.2	17.2
3	Genetic Matching	0.3	1 SD Caliper	Yes	Gen	1.3	2.3	3.3	4.3	5.3	6.3	7.3	8.3	9.3	10.3	11.3	12.3	13.3	14.3	15.3	16.3	17.3
4	Genetic Matching	0.4 2 Nearest Neighbours	None	Yes	Gen	1.4	2.4	3.4	4.4	5.4	6.4	7.4	8.4	9.4	10.4	11.4	12.4	13.4	14.4	15.4	16.4	17.4
5	Genetic Matching	0.5	0.25 SD Caliper	Yes	Gen	1.5	2.5	3.5	4.5	5.5	6.5	7.5	8.5	9.5	10.5	11.5	12.5	13.5	14.5	15.5	16.5	17.5
6	Genetic Matching	0.6	1 SD Caliper	Yes	Gen	1.6	2.6	3.6	4.6	5.6	6.6	7.6	8.6	9.6	10.6	11.6	12.6	13.6	14.6	15.6	16.6	17.6
7	Genetic Matching	0.7 1 Nearest Neighbour	None	No	Gen	1.7	2.7	3.7	4.7	5.7	6.7	7.7	8.7	9.7	10.7	11.7	12.7	13.7	14.7	15.7	16.7	17.7
8	Genetic Matching	0.8	0.5 SD Caliper	No	Gen	1.8	2.8	3.8	4.8	5.8	6.8	7.8	8.8	9.8	10.8	11.8	12.8	13.8	14.8	15.8	16.8	17.8
9	Genetic Matching	0.9	1 SD Caliper	No	Gen	1.9	2.9	3.9	4.9	5.9	6.9	7.9	8.9	9.9	10.9	11.9	12.9	13.9	14.9	15.9	16.9	17.9
10	Mahalanobis Distance Matching	0.1 1 Nearest Neighbour	None	Yes	Maha	1.1	2.1	3.1	4.1	5.1	6.1	7.1	8.1	9.1	10.1	11.1	12.1	13.1	14.1	15.1	16.1	17.1
11	Mahalanobis Distance Matching	0.2	0.25 SD Caliper	Yes	Maha	1.2	2.2	3.2	4.2	5.2	6.2	7.2	8.2	9.2	10.2	11.2	12.2	13.2	14.2	15.2	16.2	17.2
12	Mahalanobis Distance Matching	0.3	1 SD Caliper	Yes	Maha	1.3	2.3	3.3	4.3	5.3	6.3	7.3	8.3	9.3	10.3	11.3	12.3	13.3	14.3	15.3	16.3	17.3
13	Mahalanobis Distance Matching	0.4 2 Nearest Neighbours	None	Yes	Maha	1.4	2.4	3.4	4.4	5.4	6.4	7.4	8.4	9.4	10.4	11.4	12.4	13.4	14.4	15.4	16.4	17.4
14	Mahalanobis Distance Matching	0.5	0.25 SD Caliper	Yes	Maha	1.5	2.5	3.5	4.5	5.5	6.5	7.5	8.5	9.5	10.5	11.5	12.5	13.5	14.5	15.5	16.5	17.5
15	Mahalanobis Distance Matching	0.6	1 SD Caliper	Yes	Maha	1.6	2.6	3.6	4.6	5.6	6.6	7.6	8.6	9.6	10.6	11.6	12.6	13.6	14.6	15.6	16.6	17.6
16	Mahalanobis Distance Matching	0.7 1 Nearest Neighbour	None	No	Maha	1.7	2.7	3.7	4.7	5.7	6.7	7.7	8.7	9.7	10.7	11.7	12.7	13.7	14.7	15.7	16.7	17.7
17	Mahalanobis Distance Matching	0.8	0.5 SD Caliper	No	Maha	1.8	2.8	3.8	4.8	5.8	6.8	7.8	8.8	9.8	10.8	11.8	12.8	13.8	14.8	15.8	16.8	17.8
18	Mahalanobis Distance Matching	0.9	1 SD Caliper	No	Maha	1.9	2.9	3.9	4.9	5.9	6.9	7.9	8.9	9.9	10.9	11.9	12.9	13.9	14.9	15.9	16.9	17.9
19	Optimal Full Matching	0.1 1 Nearest Neighbour	None	No	OF	1.1	2.1	3.1	4.1	5.1	6.1	7.1	8.1	9.1	10.1	11.1	12.1	13.1	14.1	15.1	16.1	17.1
20	Optimal Full Matching	0.2 1 Nearest Neighbour	0.5 SD Caliper	No	OF	1.2	2.2	3.2	4.2	5.2	6.2	7.2	8.2	9.2	10.2	11.2	12.2	13.2	14.2	15.2	16.2	17.2
21	Optimal Full Matching	0.3 1 Nearest Neighbour	1 SD Caliper	No	OF	1.3	2.3	3.3	4.3	5.3	6.3	7.3	8.3	9.3	10.3	11.3	12.3	13.3	14.3	15.3	16.3	17.3